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STORIE QUATERNARIE E TERRITORI IN EVOLUZIONE

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High-resolution climatostratigraphic reconstruction at the Plio-Pleistocene transition in the Monte San Nicola type section (Sicily)

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We present a high-resolution multiproxy study to unravel climate changes during the Plio-Pleistocene transition (PPt) in the Mediterranean Sea. Our proxies rely on micropaleontological (calcareous plankton), organic geochemical (alkenones), and oxygen isotope data.

The PPt, situated between the Mid-Piacenzian Warm Period (~3 Ma) and the intensification of the North Hemisphere Glaciation (NHG) is a crucial climate transition in the Earth's history, during which the scenario progressively changed, recording a long-term cooling. To unravel the features of this important reorganization on a global scale, we analyzed the Monte San Nicola Gelasian type-section, located in the central Mediterranean area. The present work aims to understand the response of calcareous plankton at PPt and to reconstruct the environmental conditions of surface waters at orbital and millennial scale.

Our results reveal that orbital and suborbital climatic signals are well preserved in the MSNt-s. The biotic and abiotic proxies indicate relatively weak variability in surface waters during the glacial-interglacial MIS G4 to G1, followed by a pronounced amplitude increase in obliquity cycles starting from MIS 104. This finding reinforces the evidence that the first significant southward migration of the Subarctic Front in the mid-latitudes occurred during MIS 104, slightly below the GSSP. Surface waters conditions strongly varied on a precessional scale highlight modifications in surface water dynamics related to African monsoon activity and North Atlantic climate variability. Superimposed to orbital cyclicity, our record reveals the occurrence of millennial-scale variability within MIS 104 and MIS 100, correlated to North Atlantic Ice Rafted Debris events and resembling Late Pleistocene Dansgaard–Oeschger events.

Our findings provide evidence that the paleoclimate and stratigraphic signals are very well preserved in the type-section and further improve the correlation potential of the GSSP outside the type-area.

Whale fall events and fossil ambergris in the Early Pleistocene of Umbria: a new window into specialized opportunistic community of vertebrate and invertebrate

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The paleontological heritage of the Alleron area (Umbria, central Italy) is well represented by the sites of Bargiano, where a cetacean skeleton and more than 27 fossil ambergris structures (linked to the presence of sperm-whale carcasses) have been found, and Montemoro quarries (which returned three whale skeletons). The area represents a window onto a shallow (100 m-150 m) Early Pleistocene marine paleoenvironment that has been proven ideal for an investigation of the relationships among opportunistic and scavenger micro- and macrofauna in WFEs (Whale-fall events). The first and worldwide unique examples of *Ambergrisichnus alleronae* (cololite of sperm whales) were found in 2011 into Early Pleistocene clay marine deposits. The interpretation of ichnofossils was supported by several features also identified in modern ambergris, including 1) internal organization of concentric structures, 2) external shape with converging striae and bulges (rognons), 3) inclusions of squid beaks and 4) occurrence of cholic acid derivate substances. These cololites were deposited in a relatively deep (100-150m) marine environment, and the large number of structures in a restricted area was plausibly ascribed to multiple death events of sperm whales, in a range of ~100 ky. The large accumulation of cololites is still an unsolved problem. Three mass death events at least have been inferred, associated with whale carcasses sinking in relatively deep water rather than stranding. In 2016, a whale skeleton was extracted in the site of Bargiano, very close to the *Ambergrisichnus alleronae* structures, and new insights into communities of benthic foraminifera, decapods, echinoids, teleost fishes and sharks have been discovered. The analysis of six short sections located at varying distances from the whale remains and close to selected fossil ambergris cololites, highlighted changes in benthic foraminifer assemblages and allowed to identify dominant taxa connected both to bacterial growth and to nutrient accumulation in the sediment. The increase of nutrients, relative to whale biomass dispersion and evidenced by frequencies of opportunistic benthic foraminifera, led to confirm a lateral dispersion in a 10 m radius around fossil remains. The repeated overlap of WFE over time facilitated the persistence of opportunistic taxa on the sea floor, some of which assumed specialized forms, and favored their reproduction. Some recent data, as well as an overview of the events in a larger area, shed new light on the characteristics of these WFE, and some hypotheses on their origin can be proposed.

Rhodalgal carbonates from the Quaternary of Northern Italy

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We here describe in detail rhodalgal carbonates from the Quaternary of Northern Italy (Enza and Stirone rivers), which occur in unconventional settings (= high sediment-load/turbidity context). Rhodoliths formed two distinct horizons at the Enza River, separated by an inter-layer of coarse biogenic skeletal remains in a muddy matrix, including sparse rhodoliths. The first horizon is formed by a densely packed rhodolith layer of at least 50 cm in thickness and several meters of lateral continuity. Rhodoliths were both boxwork and praline morphotypes, with spheroidal shape, and their sizes varied from 2.8 up to 6.6 in diameter. The inner structure was characterized by both concentric and asymmetric development, with variable degrees of compactness. Ten rhodoliths had nuclei of different nature. The algae growth-form was encrusting to warty. Identified species were *Lithothamnion* and *Titanoderma* sp., with a rare occurrence of *Mesophyllum* sp. and another undetermined Lithophylloidea.

Conversely, at the Stirone River rhodoliths occurred sparse in a poorly sorted medium to fine sand, rich in *Pinna nobilis* in life position. Rhodoliths formed boxwork and praline, spheroidal and with only two discoidal specimens. Rhodolith varied from 2.7 up to 8.2 in diameter. Rhodoliths at Stirone always had a concentric development around a nucleus of different nature, with the occurrence of evident concentric darkened layers, due to phases of erosion and/or stasis during their development. Interestingly, some specimens showed a marked warty-to-lumpy growth-form close to the nuclei, with respect to the encrusting-type at the external part. Identified species were *Lithothamnion* sp., *Lithophyllum* sp., *Titanoderma* sp., with a rare occurrence of *Mesophyllum* sp. In both localities, although the two contexts differ, rhodoliths represent an iconic occurrence, playing a crucial role in reconstructing local paleoenvironmental evolution, able to develop both a small bed at the Enza River, or providing evidence of dynamic paleoenvironments with high sedimentation and/or turbidity rates at the Stirone River.

Isotope Geochemistry of carbonate crusts developed on Tiber fluvial sediments

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Large variations in carbon isotopes occur in carbonate crusts developed on Tiber fluvial sediments at Ponte Galeria area (Rome), formed in correspondence with anomalous circular depressions, generally ten meters wide, a few meters deep, and conical in shape. These crusts, alternating with fine alluvial sediments, emerged during the excavations for works related to the redevelopment of the area, which also brought to light a stretch of the ancient Roman road of the Via Portuense. They are what remains of the CO₂-rich waters that intermittently rose to the bottom of the Tiber valley in the past. Samples for U-Th dating provided 2650 ± 250 years for the lowest crust, about 3 m below the ground surface, and 1025 ± 275 years for that at 1 m. Samples for dating have also been used for stable isotope analysis; whereas the isotopic compositions of oxygen show little variation, those of carbon show a wide range between about 0 and -16‰ (vs. V-PDB). This range significantly extends towards more negative values the range of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ observed in travertine and tufa situated in central and southern Italy. The most ¹³C depleted samples are for carbonate crusts developed more recently, the most ¹³C enriched samples are for those formed more anciently. While the isotopic distribution should indicate that the origin of carbon of the crusts has changed over time, as a consequence of variations related to the progradation of the Tiber delta in the last 2500 years, the more negative $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ observed here can be more easily explained by a process of dissolution and reprecipitation of the more recent crusts at the expense of the older ones with the input of soil CO₂ in an open system.

The role of lithology and tectonic structures in controlling coseismic deformation inferred by DInSAR technique: the case of the 2016 Mw 6.5 Norcia earthquake

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In 2016, a significant seismic sequence struck the Central Italy Apennines, producing notable coseismic deformation and widespread surface ruptures. These were mainly associated with the 24 August Mw 6.0 and the 30 October Mw 6.5 mainshocks. The coseismic ruptures were firstly identified by field surveys and then confirmed by the analysis of satellite data, specifically via DInSAR analysis of ALOS-2 SAR imagery. This work presents a detailed map of ground deformation and coseismic ruptures associated with the activation of the M. Vettore – M. Bove Fault System (VBFS) during the October 2016 mainshock. A set of 5 geological cross-sections integrated with seismological and geodetic data have been produced to investigate the role of lithology distribution and geological structures (i.e. thrust, normal faults) on controlling the deformation patterns. Analysis of the integrated cross-sectional data reveals several recurring features, most notably a zone of subsidence affecting the hanging wall block of the VBFS. This subsidence increases in magnitude from north (Visso) to south (Castelluccio di Norcia). To the west, the subsiding area is bounded by distinct deformation patterns that vary across different sectors of the study area. Additionally, the subsidence gradually diminishes toward the emergence of thrust faults, both to the east and west. Also, an important lithological control has been recognized, with a major distribution of deformation in correspondence of carbonate multilayer and a minor (or absent) involvement of the clastic succession. The overall integrated data shows a complex deformation pattern associated with the October 2016 mainshock, which has been strongly affected by the lithological distribution and geological structures. The results demonstrate that the integration of surface geology, seismicity distribution and remote sensing data, can lead to a better understanding of the role of lithology and tectonic structures on controlling the deformation associated with seismic events.

Thematic mapping of LULC changes over 35 years in the 150-years fluvial corridor of the Sele River (Southern Italy)

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Fluvial corridor can be defined as the portion of the alluvial plain recently occupied by the river active channel in a given time-span. Unquestionably, fluvial corridors are the portions of the alluvial plains in which flood hazard is the highest. Notwithstanding this, fluvial corridors were often intensively exploited in the last decades for construction of human infrastructures and activities and for agricultural purposes, these latter due to the high fertility of alluvial soils. Mapping the Land Use-Land Cover (LULC) changes allows reconstructing the human exploitation dynamics of the fluvial corridors and highlighting the areas in which flood risk is the highest.

Among the rivers of the Campania region (Southern Italy), the Sele River is characterized by the highest flood discharge. It underwent destructive and extreme floods, such as in 1935 and 2010. In the last 150 years, the Sele R. also experienced remarkable channel adjustments, mainly consisting in narrowing up to ~120 metres, changes in channel morphology and riverbed degradation.

In this study, thematic maps of the LULC changes occurred between 1988 and 2023 in the Sele River fluvial corridor shaped in the last 150 years were produced in GIS environment. To this aim, the Sele R. active channels were digitized, by using ArcGIS 10.3 and QGIS software, from: (i) 1:50,000 scale historical maps dated back to 1870 and 1909; (ii) 1:25,000 scale topographic maps from 1955; (iii) orthophotos freely downloadable from the website www.pcn.minambiente.it, dated back to 1988; (iv) orthophotos provided by Regione Campania authority, at a nominal scale ranging from 1:10,000 to 1:5000, dated back to 1998, 2004, 2008, 2011 and 2014; and, finally, (v) Google Earth images from 2023. All the materials were previously georeferenced in UTM WGS84 coordinate system. The digitized active channels were then dissolved to obtain the fluvial corridor shaped by the Sele R. in the last 150 years.

The fluvial corridor polygon was then overlaid, in GIS environment, to the orthophotos from 1988 to 2023 to obtain LULC thematic maps at different dates by means of aerial photos visual interpretation. The results were expressed as percent of the fluvial corridor total area occupied by the considered LULC classes at different dates and allowed reconstructing the most recent history of human exploitation of the corridor and highlighting the most problematic points in terms of flood risk.

Environmental dynamics and response of the Mar Piccolo basin (Taranto, Southern Italy) to climatic and anthropogenic forcings during the Holocene: A high-resolution palynological approach

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The Holocene has been marked by significant climatic fluctuations and increasing anthropogenic pressure, particularly in coastal Mediterranean environments. Reconstructing how these systems responded to environmental forcing is crucial for understanding their long-term evolution and resilience.

This study focuses on the Mar Piccolo of Taranto (Southern Italy), a semi-enclosed marine basin historically affected by significant demographic development and long-term human presence (since Neolithic). Its geomorphological setting and restricted hydrodynamics make it a highly sensitive recorder of both natural and human-induced changes.

The main aim of this research is to reconstruct the environmental and climatic changes of the basin over the last 12,000 years through high-resolution palynological analysis, with a particular focus on dinoflagellate cysts and other non-pollen palynomorphs (NPPs) from a sediment core (S05B) and surface sediments. The integration of these proxies with pollen data from the same samples enables the identification of key climatic phases (e.g., the 8.2, 4.2, and 2.8 ka BP events) and the assessment of their impact on the water column and trophic conditions.

Results reveal alternating phases of column water destabilization, closely linked to both climate variability and local hydrological shifts. Variations in the abundance and composition of dinocyst assemblages reflect salinity changes, eutrophication trends, sea surface temperature fluctuations, and marine water exchange dynamics. Additionally, NPPs such as *Glomus*-type and *Spirogyra*-type help to identify episodes of soil erosion and increased terrestrial input. The presence of intestinal parasite eggs, such as *Trichuris*-type, recorded since the Neolithic, provides clear evidence of early human impact. Notably, these indicators intensify following the first appearance and subsequent increase of anthropogenic signals. The concurrent rise of wastewater-related taxa (e.g., *Arcella*-type) further supports the hypothesis of enhanced nutrient input and runoff associated with early agricultural activities. This case study offers valuable insights into the Holocene evolution of a semi-enclosed Mediterranean coastal basin and its response to combined climatic, hydrological, and anthropogenic drivers, aligning closely with ongoing research on Quaternary ecosystem dynamics.

Preliminary results from a stratified middle Palaeolithic open-air site in the Po Plain Loess Basin (Northern Italy)

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The reconstruction of Neanderthal settlement in Northern Italy is characterized by long-standing biases in the archaeological record, as research has traditionally focused on cave sites, primarily in the Pre-Alpine and Ligurian sectors. Despite evidence suggesting a continuous human presence throughout the Middle to Upper Pleistocene, the southern Po Plain and the Northern Apennines have remained under-investigated due to the scarcity of stratified contexts and the difficulty of interpreting disturbed open-air deposits. This presentation focuses on a new open-air site, Cava Santa Martina (Alseno, PC), located in a quarry at the northern fringe of the northern Apennines. The site consists of a large area situated on a fluvial terrace dating to the Middle Pleistocene repeatedly covered by loess strata formed during the cold and arid stages of the upper Pleistocene. A multi-layered loess–palaeosoil sequence has been partially exposed through quarrying activities. Excavations, ongoing since 2007, have revealed lithic artefacts embedded in soil horizons typically at the interface between alluvial clays and aeolian sediments. Fieldwork has confirmed multiple phases of human occupation, possibly corresponding to at least two distinct phases of the Middle Palaeolithic. Preliminary OSL dating suggests that the first occupation of the area happened in the late Middle Pleistocene around 190 ka BP, whereas the following one is dated at ca. 60 ka BP in the MIS4 of the Upper Pleistocene. The lithic artefacts are mainly made of chert and jasper from local outcrops, collected as naturally rounded and patinated nodules found in weathered gravels on the same terraces. Cava Santa Martina thus represents a rare and significant context for investigating open-air Middle Palaeolithic exploitation in the Po Plain Loess Basin during cold phases. This research highlights the importance of multidisciplinary approaches for studying open-air sites and contributes to a deeper understanding of Neanderthal settlement strategies in a landscape shaped by climatic fluctuations, limited shelter availability, and uneven resource distribution.

Stratigraphy of Middle-Late Pleistocene deposits at the Apennine margin of the Po Plain (Northern Italy), and implications for water storage in subsurface reservoirs

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The Apennine margin of the Po Plain (Northern Italy) represents one of the most densely populated areas in Italy and hosts several strategic industrial hubs of the country. The transition between the uplifting Apennines and the subsiding Po Plain is characterised by a complex system of thrusts that constitute the Pede-Apennine Thrust Front (PTF). The Apennine margin is typified by a regressive succession characterized by the upward transition from neritic clays to littoral sands and alluvial gravels. Alluvial sediments are dated to the last ~800,000 B.P. This study provides a detailed sedimentological and stratigraphic characterisation of the alluvial deposits downstream of the PTF. In this area, metric packages of gravels with thinner muds intercalations, slightly dipping (3-5°) towards N-NE, are exposed along the incised riverbed of the Secchia River. Gravel bodies exhibit an erosional basal contact and a clast-supported texture and are topped by rubified paleosols. These features suggest deposition in a high-energy fluvial system. Muddy horizons, up to 2 meters thick, have yellowish colour, subtle pebble layers and carbonate concretions. The facies interpretation suggests a well-drained floodplain environment. Subsurface stratigraphy of these deposits down to 350 m depth was reconstructed along a 12 km-long cross-section, parallel to the Secchia River. This section was obtained by correlating borehole and well data and depicts the boundary between littoral and alluvial deposits and a cyclic organization of alluvial deposits. Each cycle is characterised by gravel-mud alternations, with thickness of mud strata increasing downstream. The thickness and the degree of interconnections of fluvial channel gravels decrease in the same direction. Mud-prone sediments were deposited in a floodplain environment, with the exception of a fossiliferous horizon, tentatively attributed to MIS9, deposited in a paralic environment. Based on sparse pollen data, this cyclic organization of facies, observed in other areas of the Po Plain, is interpreted to reflect climate oscillations at the Milankovitch scale.

Fluvial channel gravels represent efficient groundwater reservoir, whereas muddy horizons may act as hydraulic barrier to fluid circulation in the subsurface. Assessing the spatial distribution and lateral continuity of these layers is crucial for groundwater management. To this aim, additional stratigraphic cross-sections are under construction for the development of a three-dimensional model of the aquifer system and for a detailed mapping of recharge areas.

Late Pleistocene vegetation history of an intermontane basin in central Italy (Colfiorito, Marche)

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As part of the CARG project Geological Sheet No. 312 “Nocera Umbra”, a continuous 60-meter sediment core was retrieved from the Colfiorito Plain (Umbria-Marche Apennines). This core was the subject of multidisciplinary studies aimed at defining the chronostratigraphy of the sediments and reconstructing the paleoenvironmental and paleoclimatic history of the area. Pollen analyses reveal the vegetation dynamics associated with the climatic oscillations corresponding to MIS 5d - MIS 2. Between 60 and 57.5 m, the pollen record indicates an open environment with steppe vegetation dominated by *Artemisia* and Poaceae, which is attributed to MIS 5d (approximately 110.6 to 108.3 ka BP) based on vegetation features similar to other long sequences from central Italy. This interpretation is supported by the presence of a tephra layer of the Phlegraean Maddaloni eruption (109.3±1.0 ka BP). Between 57.5 m and 41.5 m, forested environments, dominated by *Abies* and *Fagus* along with mesophilous broadleaved taxa, are recorded. The composition of this forest expansion is characteristic of the St Germain I phase (MIS 5c: 108.3–87.6 ka BP), as observed in other pollen records from central Italy. After a temporary phase of steppe vegetation featured by *Artemisia* and Amaranthaceae (41.5 - 37.5 m), corresponding to the stadial oscillation of MIS 5b (87.6–85.06 ka BP), the Colfiorito pollen record reveals a rapid succession of forest expansions and contractions between 37.5 m and 32.5 m. The same oscillating trend is recorded in other long pollen sequences during MIS 5a (85.06–70.4 ka BP). Between 32.5 m and the top of the core, a new remarkable expansion of steppe vegetation with *Pinus* and *Juniperus* is indicative of the open environments of the glacial phases of MIS 4 - MIS 2. Within this time interval, modest expansions of mesophilous broadleaved taxa, accompanied by *Picea*, correspond to the phase MIS 3 (57–29 ka BP). At 8.9 m depth, a radiocarbon dating yielded an age of 26,103 ± 215 cal BP. At 5.1 m depth, the disappearance of the ostracod species *Cytherissa lacustris* suggests an age successive to the Last Glacial Maximum. Considering these chronological constraints, the expansion of broadleaved trees observed in the upper 1.2 m had a Late Glacial age, precluding to the postglacial reforestation.

Geoarchaeological Insights from the Neolithic to the late Bronze Age archaeological sequence in Grotta Battifratta (Central Italy)

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Grotta Battifratta is a key archaeological significant site located in the municipality of Poggio Nativo (Rieti, Central Italy), recently investigated by Sapienza University of Rome. The cave lies along a mid-Pleistocene travertine escarpment on the Riano River's left bank, a minor Farfa River tributary, in the Sabina area and has been the focus of a multidisciplinary research project since 2021. This project combines archaeological excavations with geoarchaeological analyses to reconstruct the depositional and post-depositional processes responsible for shaping the archaeological stratigraphy, with the broader aim of linking these dynamics to human occupation phases and late Quaternary climatic variability. Ongoing fieldwork has revealed a well-preserved stratigraphic sequence documenting a long-term human presence at the site, extending from the Middle Palaeolithic through the Neolithic until the Bronze Age. Evidence from the Neolithic layers suggests a predominant focus on ritual and funerary activities, which persisted into the Bronze Age, when subsistence-related practices also became attested. From a geoarchaeological perspective, the formation of the Neolithic deposits is associated with multiple alluvial episodes that produced alternating clayey to silty organic-rich layers—containing charcoal, bone, and ceramic fragments—and reddish to brown sandy-silty sterile horizons. These sedimentary alternations reflect climatic instability, with phases of intense rainfall causing soil erosion, sediment influx, and reworking of earlier archaeological materials. These high-energy events were followed by quieter depositional phases, marked by intermittent, low-intensity water flow within a confined basin environment inside the cave. This integrated investigation highlights the critical role of geoarchaeological approaches in disentangling the complex relationships between human settlement dynamics, climatic fluctuations during the late Quaternary, and anthropogenic landscape transformation. Grotta Battifratta thus represents a key case study for reconstructing occupation continuity and environmental change in Central Apennines upland cave contexts.

Soil and paleosols in dynamic landscapes: the case study of the Montello Hill

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Paleosols are valuable tools for the reconstruction of climatic and landscape evolution at various spatial and temporal resolutions. The project examines the paleosols of the north-eastern sector of the Veneto Pre-Alps. In detail, it is envisaged to investigate the pedological evolution of the fluvial terraces of the Montello hill, the outermost relief of the Alps facing the Veneto plain. Characterising the paleosols, we aim to outline the Quaternary evolution of the area, integrating the already consolidated information about the geological, geomorphological, sedimentary and tectonic setting. The main aim is to define the Montello hill soil chronosequence and correlate it with other paleosols in the Prealpine area, through a comparison based on the pedogenic characteristics and the degree of alteration. The possible presence of loess is also checked, as an indicator of Pleistocene glacial environmental conditions. The results of the chemical analyses performed on profile M25/01, located on the second terrace of the Montello hill, are presented and compared with other profiles obtained by drilling. In the next future, the project envisages to study other paleosol profiles and to integrate the results with specific data deriving from micromorphological observations, X-ray Diffraction, X-Ray Fluorescence and the evaluation of the magnetic susceptibility of the different soils. Additionally, the second intention of the project is assessing the role of the examined paleosols within the Critical Zone in relation to their usage as a supporting substrate for wine production, which is nationally and internationally recognised. In this way, we wish to consider the possibility of defining the presence of “pedosites”, to enhance the territory appreciation.

DInSAR Coseismic deformation of the Mw 4.4 Umbertide 2023 earthquake (Central Italy)

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The Quaternary Altotiberina basin, located in the Umbrian sector of the Northern Apennines, is bordered by the Alto Tiberina Fault (ATF), a 60 km-long, ENE dipping low-angle normal fault ($<30^\circ$) that cuts through the shallow crust. Seismic activity in the Altotiberina basin is mainly characterized by swarms, light magnitude seismic sequences, and a constant rate of background seismicity.

The 2023 Umbertide seismic sequence represents the south-westernmost cluster in the instrumental seismicity of the area and includes the largest events recorded over the past 20 years. The focal mechanism of the Mw 4.4 mainshock reveals an extensional event involving two nodal planes: a 65° SW-dipping plane and a 25° NE-dipping plane. Seismicity was projected onto the geological cross-section constrained by seismic profiles. The sequence is characterized by three main events (Mw 4.3, Mw 4.4, and Mw 3.8) that align at 4 km along the ATF. Foreshocks and aftershocks are bounded in the hanging wall by the ATF and gently dip northeastward.

Despite its relatively low magnitude (Mw 4.4), coseismic deformation associated with the 2023 Umbertide was detected using Differential Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (DInSAR). Sentinel-1 data were processed with the open-source Python tool Snap2DQuake. The DInSAR analysis produced displacement maps for both the vertical and horizontal (E–W) components, revealing localized deformation in the epicentral area, with a maximum vertical displacement of 3 cm, consistent with GPS data from the near-fault TABOO observatory. In addition, time series obtained through the Small Baseline Subset (SBAS) approach were analyzed to investigate pre-seismic activity and possible preparatory processes. This demonstrates the capability of DInSAR not only to resolve subtle ground movements in low-magnitude seismic events, but also to contribute to understanding the deformation history leading up to such events.

Facies and geochemistry of Pleistocene calcareous tufa deposits of Rome (Italy)

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This study investigates the Pleistocene calcareous tufa deposits outcropping in Rome, central Italy, and examines the relationship between tufa precipitation, climate and tectonics. Within the urban context of Rome, the tufa deposits crop out at several sites, well-exposed and visible despite the secular urbanization. In addition, subsurface deposits have been documented especially in recent times, when the urban development has led to a greater knowledge of the subsoil of the city through an increase in the number of drilling and boreholes for urban management.

The tufa deposits, in part reviewed from literature and in part described for the first time, have been investigated by field surveys, petrography, mineralogy and stable isotope geochemistry. According to the geological cartography of Rome and the stratigraphy of the sites, tufa deposits are chronologically referred mostly to MIS13 and MIS11. In total nine tufa lithofacies have been described; their association and the outcrop-scale geometries allowed us to infer the depositional environments of each deposit, which can be related to low-energy (e.g., paludal, lacustrine) or high-energy (e.g. fluvial, waterfall) conditions. Stable carbon and oxygen isotope ratios have been determined, to provide clues about environmental conditions such as the sources of carbon, the temperature and the type of water that were present when they formed. Isotopic values range from about -5 to $+9\%$ vs. VPDB for carbon, and from about $+24$ to $+28\%$ vs. VSMOW for oxygen; the isotope data of different deposits are quite distinct from each other. The results suggest that the tufa was precipitated from water of meteoric origin, but at different temperatures; the large variation in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values reflects the different carbon sources for the different sites. In some cases, diagenetic processes have impacted isotopic compositions.

The spatial distribution of subsurface carbonate deposits (tufa and/or travertine), derived from the borehole IGAG database, has been also analyzed. This analysis suggests a relationship between the buried deposits and the NW-SE trending sedimentary basin of Paleo-Tiber graben.

On the *Palaeoloxodon antiquus* skulls of the Sapienza collections from Via dell'Impero (Rome, Italy): paleontology, litho-stratigraphy, microstructure and stable isotopes of tooth enamel

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During the civil construction works in the city center of Rome in the 1930s, a new street, Via dell'Impero (now Via dei Fori Imperiali), was opened in the area between Piazza Venezia and the Colosseum, leading to the dismantling of the Velia hill. Several paleontological remains were discovered, including skulls of *Palaeoloxodon antiquus*, and several remains of *Cervus elaphus*, *Bos primigenius*, *Hippopotamus amphibius*.

Two skulls of *Palaeoloxodon antiquus* from Via dell'Impero are currently stored in two museums at the Sapienza University of Rome: the first, a well preserved and nearly intact adult specimen, is exhibited at the Museo delle Origini; the second, a partially preserved juvenile individual, is housed at the Museo Universitario di Scienze della Terra (MUST). Both skulls preserve a sandy-clayey sediment, deposited contemporaneously with their burial, inside the bone cavities or encrusting the surfaces of the cranial bone.

In this work we describe these fossil remains, their current preservation status, and their biochronological and palaeoecological significance in the context of the Roman Basin. We also present the results of the litho-stratigraphic revision of the Velia hill, as well as mineralogical and petrographic studies on the sediments preserved in the bone cavities of the skulls, in order to add information on the sedimentary formation of the original deposit and to provide further chronological constraints of the deposit, that has been recently attributed to MIS 11c (ca. 400 ka). Microstructure and composition of tooth enamel have been determined by scanning electron microscopy and X-ray powder diffraction. The palaeoenvironmental conditions of the site have been inferred from the stable (C and O) isotope analysis of the carbonate fraction of tooth enamel.

A diachronic overview of the middle and late Villafranchian large mammal dispersal events

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The Quaternary is a time of substantial climatic and environmental changes, which are reflected in the response of the biota. In turn, relating this response to the geological time is crucial for understanding the pace and magnitude of the change and correlating the record of distant geographic regions. For historical and practical reasons, large mammals are widely used for biochronological correlations and palaeoecological reconstructions of the Quaternary. In particular, the establishment of local biochronological schemes in different countries and the definition of large mammal “dispersal events” were most influential contributions on Plio-Pleistocene large mammal biochronology of Europe. Biochronological schemes and events are constantly reconsidered and updated, primarily following the availability of both new chronologies for important localities and revised or new taxonomic attributions. Here, we present updated considerations on the middle and late Villafranchian faunal turnovers, starting with a diachronic revision of the two dispersal events recognized in the 1980s as denoting such faunal renewals, the “Elephant-*Equus* event” and the “Wolf event”, then highlighting the importance of integrating and correlating biochronological schemes from distant areas. In particular, the recently established Late Pliocene–Middle Pleistocene large mammal Faunal Units of Greece allow us to discuss similarities and differences with respect to relevant Italian and Western European schemes and to better track both dispersal events across Southern Europe.

A century of paleoanthropological research at Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania: A retrospective on scientific endeavours after the Leakeys' Expedition

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Olduvai Gorge, located in northern Tanzania, is a world-renowned paleoanthropological and paleontological site. It has made significant contributions to our understanding of human evolution, paleoenvironmental changes, faunal diversity, and geological history over the past 2 million years. The site was first discovered in 1911 by a German entomologist, but its unique paleoanthropological importance was revealed through the meticulous work of the Leakey family (Louis and Mary Leakey) conducted between 1913 and 1985. Leakeys' research exploration at the site resulted in the discovery of various hominin species including *Paranthropus boisei*, *Homo habilis*, and *Homo erectus* that changed the global paradigm of human evolutionary history. They also documented the presence of stone tools (Early, Middle, and Later Stone Age), extinct and extant vertebrate remains, and reconstructed paleoenvironmental changes in the area. The scientific foundation they laid down attracted many research teams such as Olduvai Geochronology Archaeology Project (OGAP), Olduvai Landscape Palaeoanthropology Project (OLAPP), The Olduvai Gorge Paleoecology and Palaeoanthropology Project (TOPPP), and Tanzania Human Origins Research (THOR). These new research teams are discussed herein in light of their new methodological approaches, discovery, and contribution to the advancement of human evolution in Africa.

Geological data to define the presence of capable faults in urbanised areas of the central Apennines

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Active and capable faulting in the central Apennine chain results from the ongoing extensional tectonic regime. Seismic microzonation supports the management of this issue by guiding actions to mitigate the risk of ground surface displacement. We present two case studies located a few tens of km S and SE of L'Aquila. Our aim is to assess potential surface displacement associated with normal faulting through detailed analysis of known and presumed capable fault branches.

Rocca di Mezzo is located on the Altopiano delle Rocche. A presumed active normal fault is hypothesized in the western portion of the village, based on borehole data suggesting a possible abrupt depth variation in the carbonate bedrock, supposed to be caused by recent normal fault displacements. Given the proximity (just a few km in plain view) to the Ovindoli-Piani di Pezza active fault system, this supposed fault would represent a further splay of the main structure. To verify the actual existence of this fault branch, we performed detailed geological investigations. Field analyses revealed no evidence of extensional faulting in the area where the fault branch is hypothesised. Shear planes affecting pre-Quaternary limestone bedrock were associated only with reverse faulting, attributed to the compressive tectonic phase currently inactive. Moreover, borehole data and field observations allowed the reconstruction of the geometry of the interface between Quaternary deposits and the underlying carbonate bedrock, revealing a gradual general deepening of the carbonate substratum, as resulting solely from just the bedrock attitude. Moreover, a trench excavated across the trace of the supposed fault revealed a late Holocene lacustrine sequence which is not displaced by any fault plane.

The village of Castel di Ieri, located in the Subequana Valley, is affected by a segment of the Middle Aterno Valley-Subequana Valley active fault system. However, the trace of the fault within the village has not been defined at the scale suitable for seismic microzonation studies. Detailed geological surveys allowed to identify a complex 70 m-wide fault zone within the village, comprising at least four fault splays. We performed a trench in the village intercepting a fault plane that affects Early Pleistocene lacustrine deposits. A second fault splay was identified a few meters to the east, placing the carbonate bedrock in contact with the same lacustrine sequence. Further splays are defined by the presence of aligned shear planes affecting both the bedrock and the Early Pleistocene lake deposits. As a whole, these case studies highlight the importance of acquiring robust geological field evidence before hypothesising the presence of an active and capable fault.

***Gulo gulo* from the Late Upper Palaeolithic Levels (latest Pleistocene) of Badanj Rockshelter (Bosnia and Herzegovina): Paleoenvironmental and paleobiogeographic considerations**

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The modern wolverine *Gulo gulo* is the largest species within the family of Mustelidae, with a body length ranging from 0.65 to 1.05 meters. The wolverine is considered a circumboreal animal, with a geographical distribution spanning from northern Eurasia (Russia, Mongolia, northern China, and Scandinavia) to the northern regions of North America (Alaska, Canada, and the western United States, including Wyoming, Idaho, Montana, Washington, Oregon, and California). The wolverine is regarded as a key species for assessing the effects of Pleistocene climatic fluctuations, as it is strongly associated with cold climates and glacial environments. Its current distribution suggests that the presence of wolverine fossils at lower latitudes reflects past climatic conditions, with cooler temperatures on average than those of today. Consequently, the wolverine has long been recognized as a proxy for cold climates, playing an important role in studies of Quaternary climatic changes.

In the course of recent analyses of faunal remains from the late Upper Palaeolithic (latest Pleistocene) rockshelter of Badanj (Bosnia and Herzegovina), housed at the National Museum of Bosnia and Herzegovina in Sarajevo, two wolverine remains have been identified. These are among the southernmost occurrences of the wolverine in Europe. This research is part of the project entitled “AFTER THE ICE: Forager Uses of “Persistent Places” in the Late Upper Palaeolithic of the Circum-Adriatic Region: Perspectives from the Riparo Tagliente (Verona, Italy) and Badanj (Bosnia and Herzegovina)”. The project aims to understand how human groups navigated changing climatic and environmental conditions in millennia following the Last Glacial Maximum in Italy and the Balkans. Based on the current dating evidence, the occupation at Badanj primarily falls in the duration of the Bølling-Allerød interstadials (~14.7–12.7 kya cal BP). Yet, the presence of the wolverine may point to the record of currently undated colder spells in the site’s sequence, with temperatures significantly lower than those characterizing the region today.

Reevaluating the tephrostratigraphy of Riparo l'Oscurusciuto, Gravina di Ginosa, Italy

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Riparo l'Oscurusciuto (Ginosa, Apulia, Italy) hosts a rich Middle Paleolithic stratigraphic record, consisting of lithic assemblages, fireplaces, and faunal remains, and was occupied discontinuously by Neanderthals during Marine Isotope Stage (MIS) 3. The part of the stratigraphic record excavated so far is encompassed in a ~20-25 kyr time interval, comprised between ~42.7 BP and ~65 ka, based on i) ¹⁴C ages measured on bones collagen at the base of the uppermost (SU-1) stratigraphic unit, ii) OSL dates, and iii) on the correlation of SU-14 with the Mount Epomeo Green Tuff (MEGT)/Y-7 tephra layer. However, recent studies highlighted that the MEGT and Y-7 represent two, geochemically similar but temporally distinguished eruptions respectively dated at ~56 ka (MEGT) and ~60 ka (Y-7), thus questioning one of the key-constraints of the age model of the Oscurusciuto sequence. In the framework of the “*Last Neanderthals*” ERC Synergy Grant project, Riparo l'Oscurusciuto is undergoing new investigations and excavations to better refine the site's chronology, that is likely to span through the end of MIS 4 as well. To reach this goal, new geochronological constraints are needed.

With this purpose, a new sampling campaign for tephra and crypto-tephra analysis, including both glass and minerals major, minor, and trace element composition determination and, possibly, direct ⁴⁰Ar/³⁹Ar dating, have been undertaken. The preliminary results of the new tephrostratigraphic investigations at Riparo l'Oscurusciuto are here presented for the first time.

Unravelling the complex history of *Dama*-like deer from the Quaternary of Europe: historical perspectives and new evidence

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The term *Dama*-like deer refers to the group of small to mid-sized cervids with three or four pointed and unpalmed antlers from the Plio-Pleistocene of Europe. Although the scientific community has not yet unanimously agreed on the taxonomy and phylogenetic relationships among these deer, they are commonly referred to the genus *Pseudodama*. Six species were initially assigned to this genus, divided in two distinct lineages, one restricted to Italy comprising *P. lyra*, *P. nestii* and *P. farnetensis*, and one to France comprising *P. pardinensis*, *P. philisi* (= *P. rhenana*) and *P. perolensis*. Another form of *Dama*-like deer, namely *P. vallonnetensis*, was described for the first time in the locality of Le Vallonnet (France). This species is nowadays commonly acknowledged as the most derived form of the genus. Several discussions have been raised regarding possible synonyms among different taxa of the group by many authors. Hereby, we present the state of the art regarding the taxonomy of the group, by addressing historical perspectives in the view of new data, investigating possible synonymies between different species and reconstructing the biogeographical background of the genus in Europe, with a special focus in the latest Early Pleistocene.

Il contributo dell'archeologia allo studio della trasformazione del paesaggio: il caso dell'antico di municipio di Trebiae (Trevi, PG)

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Since 2015, the Chair of Christian and Medieval Archaeology at the University of Perugia has been conducting stratigraphic excavations at the locality of Pietrarossa, in the plain below the present-day town of Trevi, in the Province of Perugia. The investigations, in addition to definitively resolving the long-standing question of the exact location of the Roman center of Trebiae, have made it possible to grasp the impact that the transformations of the landscape had on the evolution of the municipium over the centuries. The study, through the contribution of archaeological research and thanks to the comparison with geological and paleoseismological analyses conducted in contexts comparable to the Trevan context, reconstructs a sequence of traumatic events that destructured the city, otherwise impossible to fully grasp. A careful analysis of the excavation data has made it possible to recognize in the area of the settlement both alluvial deposits and traces compatible with seismic phenomena, such as particular structural lesions and static repairs to structures, which contributed significantly to the progressive abandonment of the site by its inhabitants.

During the 3rd century B.C., the opening of the Via Flaminia and the consequent colonization by the Viritanian settlers led to the forced abandonment of the pre-Roman site, located on the hill on which today's Trevi stands, with the consequent relocation of the settlement downstream, along the consular road and close to the river Clitunno. Due to its highly strategic position with respect to road and river routes, the center became an important commercial hub. The settlement was probably equipped with a port or a landing place, which allowed goods to be easily transshipped from the river Clitunno to the Via Flaminia, according to a perfectly integrated and interconnected infrastructure system. Starting in late antiquity, the gradual abandonment of water embankment works by the central government generated serious hydrographic instability in the lowland areas. Extreme meteorological events, together with a very intense seismic crisis, led to the complete collapse of the infrastructural system and led to the formation of a vast marshy plague that in the second half of the 5th century A.D. extended almost uninterruptedly from the Sorgenti del Clitunno to the gates of Foligno. These phenomena contributed in an important way to the profound weakening of the city of Trebiae and its resources, so much so that its inhabitants gradually recovered the site of the ancient Umbrian settlement. The same topographical position that had favored the genesis and development of the Roman-era settlement became the primary cause of its slow but inexorable decline.

The Middle Palaeolithic in the Berici Hills: contribution to the archaeozoological study of the large mammals of Grotta Maggiore di San Bernardino (Vicenza)

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The Berici Hills (VI) karstic plateau has an abundant archive of prehistoric archaeological sites. It assumes a fundamental role on the study of the anthropic settlement since the Middle Palaeolithic and the environments occupied by human groups. This research aims to contribute to the study of these topics through the presentation of the archaeozoological assemblage from Grotta Maggiore di San Bernardino (Mossano). The datings cover a chronological span that goes from the late Middle Palaeolithic (unit II) to the full Middle Palaeolithic (unit VIII÷VII) in MIS 6 and MIS 7. Here are conserved traces of the most ancient human settlements in the whole Berici Hills plateau. For some of the archaeological units, the archaeozoological and taphonomical analysis allowed to identify the Neanderthal groups as the main agent of accumulation of faunal remains. Neanderthals has left traces on exploitation of medium-large size ungulates, bear and beaver, species that are documented through the entire archaeological sequence. Usually, the ungulates of medium and large size (*Alces alces*, *Cervus elaphus*, *Capreolus capreolus*, *Bos/Bison*, *Capra ibex*, *Rupicapra rupicapra*, *Sus scrofa*, *Stephanorinus* sp., and *Rhinoceros* sp.) dominate in San Bernardino's anthropic units while carnivores (*Ursus spelaeus*, *Ursus arctos*, *Canis lupus*, *Vulpes vulpes*, *Panthera pardus*, *Lynx lynx*, *Felis silvestris*, *Lutra lutra* and *Martes* sp.) are less abundant. Lagomorpha (*Lepus* sp.) and large-size rodents (*Castor fiber* and *Marmota marmota*) are also documented; anthropic traces have been identified on the bone surfaces of these latter. In units where the accumulation of faunal remains is partially attributable to the human's action, there is an increase of carnivores compared to ungulates, in addition to a clear reduction in the number of faunal remains. Thanks to the taxonomical identification of faunal remains, it was possible, in a nutshell, to reconstruct the palaeoenvironment context around the site, consistently with the three climatic cycles recognised through the archaeological sequence on a multidisciplinary basis.

Geological map of the Pleistocene Volcano of Monte Amiata (Southern Tuscany, Italy)

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Monte Amiata (305–231 ka; Italy) is an uncommon example of an entirely effusive silicic (mainly trachytic) composite volcano. A detailed geological map (1:25,000 scale) based on Unconformity Bounded Stratigraphic Unit criteria is presented accompanied by volcano-tectonic, stratigraphic relationship, and volcano evolution schemes. The volcanic facies analysis and structural analysis criteria have been applied to decipher Monte Amiata's geological evolution and structure, and to infer the relations between volcanism and regional tectonics. Based on the occurrence of a first-order geological unconformity representing a paleo-weathering surface of paleoclimatic significance, two major volcanic stratigraphic units and seven phases of activity are recognized.

Reconstruction of sea surface temperatures during the Late Pleistocene and Holocene in the Sicily Channel

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This study reconstructs Sea Surface Temperature (SST) oscillations over the last 20 kyr using marine sediment record from the Sicily Channel, documenting climatic variability in the central Mediterranean. We identified significant paleoclimatic events marked by changes in planktonic foraminiferal assemblages and in SST signal, showing a long-term trend in temperature increase over the last 20 kyr, from 8°C to nearly 22°C, with an average of 16°C, punctuated by prominent short-term changes in SST signature.

We analysed the gravity core ND11_2013 (475 m water depth) from the NW Sicily Channel, recovered during the NEXTDATA 2013 oceanographic cruise aboard R/V CNR-Urania. The 489 cm-long core consists of grey hemipelagic sediments. This research integrates geochemical (Mg/Ca ratio on planktonic foraminifers *Globigerina bulloides* and *Globigerinoides ruber* white) and quantitative planktonic foraminifera analyses, supported by high-resolution AMS14C dating.

The climatic phases identified are as follows: Last Glacial Maximum (19.8-17.3 kyr BP), Heinrich Stadial 1 (17.3-14.7 kyr BP, cyclic pattern HS1a, HS1b, HS1c), Bølling-Allerød (14.7-12.5 kyr BP), Younger Dryas (12.5-11.5 kyr BP), Sapropel S1 like (10-6.4 kyr BP) and over the last 6.4 kyr BP the warm Early Bronze Age event (4.4-3.8 kyr BP), the Roman Period (2.4-1.4 kyr BP), and the Little Ice Age (700-100 yr BP).

The results were compared with data from the Alboran Sea and Balearic area, revealing strong similarities in both short- and long-term trends, reinforcing the validity of the findings.

This research has been also financially supported by ERC Consolidator TIMED project (REP-683237) and by Progetto di Ricerca Libera 2021 - PSVGEOFISIC, INGV.

Geomorphological evidence of different Quaternary Glacial Periods in the Northern Apennines (Mt. Aiona, Liguria)

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The Northern Apennines were widely glaciated during the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM), with the main valleys and the highest slopes covered by valley glaciers. Late Pleistocene glaciers deeply sculpted the landscape, leaving clear traces of their maximum positions, particularly well preserved on north-facing valley heads. These relict landforms along the Northern Apennines mountain chain have been recognized and investigated since the end of the 19th Century, and there are few age constraints to establish their precise ages only in Apuan Alps (Tuscany), while none of the available dates extend back to the LGM. This paper focuses on the first geomorphological research performed in the northern slopes of Mt. Aiona, in the Aveto Regional Park (Liguria). This represents an area of strategic importance because far more widespread are the remains of the last glacial episodes (glacial moraines, cirques and erratic boulders). The study is part of the GLAMED project, conducted by a joint team of researchers from different universities. Here we provide new data for better constraining the LGM in the Northern Apennines and for contributing to fill a critical gap of information regarding the older glacial episodes. In fact, in a number of places the existence of several episodes of glaciation is suggested by the occurrence of a sequence of moraine ridges and erratic boulders at different altitudes in the same valley. The first glacial event (pre-Wurmian glaciation, probably MIS 6) is characterized by moraine deposits and erratic boulders whose position and distribution contrasts with the actual orographic configuration and only few erosional landforms at high altitude, like sheepback rocks (no cirques). The soils of these moraines are well developed. The second glacial phase (LGM) is characterized by small palaeo-glaciers with the reconstructed Equilibrium Line Altitudes (ELAs) range from ~1400 m a.s.l on northerly facing slopes, and evident cirques and morenic deposits which frequently preserve their original morphology forming lateral and frontal ridges. The soils of these moraines are weakly developed. Future ¹⁰Be exposure-age dating of some selected erratic boulders located on key geomorphological sites in the area will constrain the reconstruction of these glaciers on Mt. Aiona.

GLAMED project attempts to decipher the Pleistocene glaciations in the Apennine mountains (Italian peninsula)

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Traces of Pleistocene glaciations can be found along the entire length of the Italian peninsula, from the Ligurian Apennines in the north to the mountains of Basilicata and Calabria in the south. Most landforms of glacial origin in the Apennines have traditionally been attributed to the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) or, more broadly, to the Würmian glaciation. Numerical age control such as surface exposure or radiocarbon dating, however, is available only at very few sites and therefore both the extent and the exact timing of Pleistocene glaciations remain incompletely understood. “Glaciers of the Mediterranean - GLAMED” is a new project, funded by the Department of Geosciences of the University of Padua, which aims to (1) summarise the current state of knowledge about Pleistocene glaciations in the Apennines and structure glacial features reported in the literature in a geodatabase, and (2) provide new geomorphological and geochronological data from key sites, where the timing or extent of glaciation is still debated.

This contribution gives an overview about the current state of the GLAMED project, shows the progress of the database implementation, and discusses new data from two sites with ongoing field campaigns. In the northern part of the mountain range (Ligurian Apennines), recent surveys have shown evidence for a wide-spread pre-LGM glaciation (possibly MIS 6) with a much larger ice extent than during the LGM. In the Southern Apennines (Basilicata, Calabria), on the other hand, a new reconstruction of the LGM glaciers in the Sirino massif will be presented and the influence of local and regional climatic factors on the distribution of glacier Equilibrium Line Altitudes (ELAs) will be discussed.

Glacitectonic findings in the lower Astico Valley, Southern Alps (NE Italy)

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Glacitectonics encompasses the deformation of sediments and bedrock induced by glacial processes, primarily the mechanical forces associated with the movement and pressure of ice masses. These deformations, which include folding, faulting, thrusting, and shearing, occur at various scales and reflect the dynamic interaction between glaciers and the substrates over which they advance. Glacitectonic structures provide insights into subglacial stress regimes, ice dynamics, basal conditions, and the nature of the substrate, as well as into the extent and dynamics of glaciations. The recognition and study of glacitectonic features have gained increasing attention in recent decades, despite the fact that the rugged topography and tectonically complex setting of the European Alps pose challenges to their identification. A few glacitectonic findings have been documented, particularly in glacial forelands and marginal zones.

The lower Astico Valley, situated in the southeastern sector of the Southern Alps (Italy), forms a transitional corridor between the carbonate Sette Comuni Plateau and the adjacent Venetian alluvial plain. Quaternary sedimentation is largely the result of glacial and glaciofluvial processes, especially during the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM; ~27–18 ka), when a lobe of the Adige Glacier descended through the Carbonare Saddle (1087 m a.s.l.) and flowed ~26 km downstream, leaving behind a prominent moraine system. Flanking slopes connecting the valley to the Sette Comuni Plateau contributed significantly to colluvial and alluvial fan deposits, particularly during interstadial phases. A few hundred meters upstream of the inner terminal moraine two outcrops along the Astico river incision reveal six distinct sedimentary units. The stratigraphy records the existence of a lacustrine basin, predating the LGM glacier, where silts and clays were deposited. This was followed by the accumulation of fluvial sands. Subsequently, the Astico Glacier overrode the sequence, depositing two distinct till units corresponding to different retreat/readvance phases. Subglacial stresses deformed the entire stratigraphic succession up to the upper till, which is sealed by fluvioglacial gravels related to ice retreat. Recognized glacitectonic features include a thrust duplex system with horseback folding, small-scale normal and reverse faults, graben structures and mesoscale folds with tilted axis. Additionally, fracture systems and sedimentary dikes formed by sand fluidization have been observed, possibly indicating a pre-LGM seismic event.

Evaluating *Quercus* pollen as a valuable archive of past UV-B Levels in the Central Mediterranean: Insights from comparative infrared spectroscopy analyses and links to paleoclimatic events

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Ultraviolet-absorbing compounds (UACs) in the exine of pollen and spores increase with prolonged and elevated exposure to ultraviolet B (UV-B) radiation. This correlation has been extensively studied using transmission Fourier-transform infrared microscopy (transmission micro-FTIR), mainly on *Lycopodium* spores and airborne *Pinus* pollen. However, transmission micro-FTIR is prone to infrared light scattering, which can distort spectra and reduce reproducibility. Additionally, bisaccate pollen, such as that from *Pinus*, can travel long distances, potentially misrepresenting local UV-B conditions. This study compares transmission and attenuated total reflection (ATR) micro-FTIR techniques to assess their reproducibility and explores *Quercus* pollen as a local UV-B proxy in the Central Mediterranean. The macromolecular composition of individual and clustered pollen grains—fresh (in situ), trapped (in mosses), and fossilized (from sediments)—is analyzed following various chemical treatments. Results show that ATR micro-FTIR offers greater reproducibility, confirming its value for chemo-palynological studies. *Quercus ilex* pollen consistently shows UAC-related absorption bands in both modern and fossil samples, with these signatures remaining stable after treatment with hydrochloric acid, hydrofluoric acid, and sodium hydroxide. Comparisons with fresh and moss-trapped *Q. cerris* and *Q. pubescens* pollen support these findings. The data suggest that relative UAC concentrations in *Quercus* exine reflect cumulative UV-B exposure, making *Quercus* pollen a reliable local proxy for reconstructing past UV-B levels in the Central Mediterranean. The second part of this study compares UV-B trends with modeled solar irradiance, sea surface temperature variations, and archived paleoclimatic events to explore interactions among these factors and their connection to past vegetation and sedimentological dynamics in the region.

Frame by frame: A video of the excavations of *Mammuthus primigenius* in Tarquinia (1963) rediscovered

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On March 1963 a skull with the damaged right tusk and the mandible of a proboscidean was found at Casale Terzolo, near Tarquinia (northern Latium, central Italy). Pierluigi Ambrosetti, who led the excavations, referred the material to as *Elephas primigenius*, as at that time the woolly mammoth was named. The author, pending a stratigraphical study, referred the fossil to the Tyrrhenian I *sensu* Blanc (1958). In 2005, Palombo and Ferretti confirmed the taxonomic attribution of the late Middle Pleistocene proboscidean from Tarquinia considered as one of the earliest *Mammuthus primigenius* from Italy. The skull and the mandible are stored at MUST (Museo Universitario di Scienze della Terra) and will be exposed in the Maccagno room at the third floor of the museum, at present under construction.

Ambrosetti was active at Sapienza University during the 1960s, before moving to Perugia University, where he worked until his retirement. Recently, the colleagues Angela Baldanza and Marco Cherin gave me access to part of Ambrosetti's archive, in particular the material referable at his time in Rome. Many interesting documents come out, and, of special interest, three films referable - as written in pencil on the boxes, to different phases of the excavations at Tarquinia. This interesting document will be studied and presented.

Pleistocene evolution of Molentargius beach ridges system (S Sardinia). Insight into sea level changes during MIS 5

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Beach ridges are among the most sensitive sedimentary systems to both low- and high-frequency sea-level fluctuations. The island of Sardinia (Central Mediterranean Sea) provides evidence of continuous beach ridge progradation during the MIS 5e highstand (135–115 ka). Recent studies have identified two distinct marine highstands associated with MIS 5e (~125 ka) and MIS 5c (~100 ka), separated by erosional surfaces, with MIS 5c unconformably overlying the MIS 5e deposits.

This stratigraphic relationship contrasts with the globally accepted sea-level curve, which places the MIS 5e highstand at +3 to +5 m above present sea level and MIS 5c at approximately -20 m. This discrepancy cannot be explained solely by tectonic uplift. Moreover, the precise position and character of the MIS 5c highstand remain debated and less well constrained compared to MIS 5e.

A Pleistocene beach ridge outcrop at Molentargius (Cagliari, South Sardinia), generally attributed to MIS 5, has been investigated in detail through two continuous cores and three 3-meter-deep wells. The entire succession and all cores were sampled for high-resolution luminescence dating, aiming to constrain the system's evolution and detect evidence of high-frequency sea-level changes.

The conglomeratic strata consist of well-rounded, openwork granite clasts with low-angle cross-stratification observable at the outcrop scale. Sandstone units are coarse- to medium-grained with trough and planar cross-bedding, while fine-grained sandstone and muddy layers appear only in the inland parts and in the lower sections of the cores. Three relict gravel-mixed beach systems located above the present high tide level were identified. These are organized into 3-meter-thick, prograding stacked units, separated by flooding surfaces and interpreted as parasequences.

Preliminary luminescence ages indicate distinct phases of beach ridge formation associated with MIS 5e (~125 ka), MIS 5c (~100 ka), and early MIS 5a (~81 ka), each marked by significant flooding events and brief episodes of erosion. Following the MIS 5e maximum flooding, beach ridges formed during subsequent sea-level pulses, likely linked to higher-frequency fluctuations within MIS 5.

Morpho-sedimentary analysis of late-Quaternary deposits in the Ventotene insular shelf

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Studies concerning the Quaternary have great importance as they help us to understand the effects of global climate changes, linked to several glacial and interglacial cycles. These oscillations shaped the current morpho-stratigraphic setting of continental and insular shelves worldwide. This work focuses on the insular shelf surrounding Ventotene and Santo Stefano islands, located in the eastern sector of the Pontine Archipelago (Central Tyrrhenian Sea). These islands represent the emerging portions of a large volcanic edifice emplaced in a subsiding intraslope basin and affected by a caldera-forming eruption around 0.3 Ma. The data employed in this study, including both newly acquired and pre-existing datasets, were collected through the CARG and MaGIC project surveys, respectively. The methodological approach involved an integrated analysis of high-resolution bathymetric data, backscatter (acquired using both Multibeam and Side Scan Sonar sensors), and sedimentological analysis of seafloor samples. The observations have highlighted that the shelf has been strongly influenced by erosional and depositional processes during the last emi-eustatic cycle. Moreover, this analysis compared with similar studies performed in the nearby Western Pontine Islands has enabled us to identify different depositional units. The first three units are found between the coastline and -40 m, encompassing: 1- littoral wedge deposits mainly composed of gravelly-sandy volcanoclastic sediments; 2- marine phanerogam meadows; 3- indistinct volcanic substrate colonized by marine phanerogams. The other depositional units are located at depths ranging from 50 to 150 m and consist of: 4- organogenic lithoid bodies encrusted by coralligenous; from 5 to 7- bioclastic deposits due to intrabasinal sedimentation, bioherm dismantling and locally reworked by bottom currents; 8- palimpsest deposits; in deeper areas (> -120 m), mud deposits dominate (unit 9). The result of this study will also contribute to the realization of the new geological map at 1:50.000 scale for the CARG Project.

Biochronology of Italian Bovini: Current perspectives and palaeoenvironmental implications

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Bovini is among the most successful tribes of bovids as testified by their extremely rich fossil record. The succession and turnover of Bovini taxa in Italy closely reflect the major palaeoenvironmental shifts that affected the peninsula, highlighting the sensitivity of bovid communities to climatic oscillations and habitat dynamics. Although the earliest stem-Bovini may have appeared already in the Early Pliocene (e.g., Val di Pugna, Tuscany), the evolutionary history of Italian crown-Bovini begins at the Plio-Pleistocene boundary (middle Villafranchian) with the first appearance of the *Leptobos stenometopon–elatus–merlai* group (*L. gr. SEM*) in sites such as Triversa (Piedmont), Montopoli (Tuscany), and Pantalla (Umbria). At the beginning of the Pleistocene, the intensification of Northern Hemisphere Glaciations brought cooler and more arid climates. As the last forested Neogene habitats shrank, *L. gr. SEM* disappeared, replaced by the *Leptobos etruscus–vallisarni* group (*L. gr. EV*). These forms, better suited to the new drier conditions, characterized the late Villafranchian faunal assemblages of the peninsula, being found in the famous localities of Olivola, Upper Valdarno and Val di Chiana basins (Tuscany). Continued climatic deterioration allowed the westward dispersal of several Asian ungulates, including the first representatives of *Bison*. By the end of the late Villafranchian, primitive bison—assigned to the subgenus *Bison* (*Eobison*)—replaced *L. gr. EV*, as evidenced by the rich collections from Pietrafitta (Umbria) and Pirro Nord (Apulia), where *Bison* is the sole large bovid recorded. New glacial pulses around 1.2 Ma triggered another major turnover, initiating the Epivillafranchian biochron. The first “true” bison, *Bison* (*Bison*) *schoetensacki*, entered Europe during this period but became widespread in Italy only during the Galerian (ca. 0.8 Ma), as documented by the large collection from Isernia La Pineta (Molise). By 0.5–0.4 Ma, Bovini in Italy were mainly represented by *Bison priscus* and *Bos primigenius*. While the former likely dispersed in the peninsula intermittently during glacial stages, the aurochs (*B. primigenius*) was a common and persistent element of many late Galerian–Aurelian localities, including Fontana Ranuccio and Polledrara di Cecanibbio (Latium), and Grotta Romanelli (Apulia), among others. During Middle and Late Pleistocene interglacials, Italy was also sporadically inhabited by the warm-adapted Bubalini with Asian affinities, *Bubalus* and *Hemibos*, indicated by their remains from Ponte Galeria and Polledrara di Cecanibbio (Latium).

ÇoraDrill: Reconstructing the Eruptive History of Erciyes volcano and the paleoclimate of Central Anatolia by drilling sediment cores within the Çora Maar Crater (Turkey)

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The ÇoraDrill project aims to reconstruct the late Pleistocene and Holocene eruptive history of the active Erciyes volcano as well as the climate history of Central Anatolia by retrieving lake sediment cores within the Çora maar crater, Turkey. By investigating tephra layers deposited within the lacustrine sedimentary infill sequence (e.g., stratigraphy, geochronological, and geochemical analyses), the project will identify and characterise previously unrecognized Erciyes explosive eruptions. This research will not only enhance volcanic risk assessments in the Cappadocia region by reconstructing the volcanic history of Erciyes but also enable tephra correlations to distal records (e.g., Black Sea) using the glass chemical fingerprints, which will fill the gaps in the tephrostratigraphic framework of Eastern Europe. These correlations will allow a better estimation of the Erciyes eruption volumes and magnitudes, allowing more accurate simulations of volcanic ash dispersal and improving modelled forecasts of potential future eruptions. The tephra layers within the Çora maar sedimentary sequence will be dated directly by radiogenic methods such as Ar/Ar and U-Th, and by radiocarbon dating the lacustrine sediments. Integrating the newly established chronology of Erciyes explosive eruptions with the analyses of sedimentary proxies (e.g., pollen, stable isotopes, fossils, and organic matter) from the lacustrine sequence, the environmental evolution of the Çora area will be reconstructed, thereby contributing to the understanding of the climate fluctuations and their impacts in the Central Anatolia, including to the first hominid civilisations established in that strategic region of Eurasia. The results of ÇoraDrill will be disseminated following the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) procedures in different ways (scientific articles, conferences, workshops, seminars, etc). Additionally, the project will promote the engagement of Turkish authorities, increase public awareness through different outreach activities, and strengthen risk mitigation strategies, and help support the establishment of a volcanological observatory in Turkey.

Quaternary glaciation in the Terragnolo and Posina Valleys: Interaction between the Atesino Glacier and the Local Monte Pasubio Glacier

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The Terragnolo and Posina Valleys, located around the Monte Pasubio massif, exhibit a complex glacial history linked to glacier expansion and retreat during the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM). The Terragnolo Valley, a left tributary of the Adige Valley near Rovereto, extends east-west at the foot of Monte Pasubio before shifting NNW-SSE towards the Borcola Pass, which connects it to the Posina Valley. The Terragnolo Valley is characterized by glacial deposits associated with the LGM. The valley's morphology and sediment distribution reflect the interaction between the Adige Valley trunk glacier, which is marked by highly polygenic deposits, and the local Monte Pasubio glacier, where carbonate lithologies are almost exclusively present. Studying this interaction provides insights into the dynamics of two glacial systems of very different scales. The analysis, based on LiDAR-derived Digital Terrain Models (DTMs) and field surveys, allowed for the characterization of glacial deposits. The data suggest that the valley underwent phases of damming, infilling, and drainage, likely linked to the evolution of the Atesino Glacier. Clear evidence of this is the presence of overconsolidated glacial deposits, suggesting the existence of a lake basin that was later overridden by the advancing Adige Glacier, which reached an elevation of 1400 m. Investigations in the Valle dei Lombardi, a NNW-SSE oriented tributary of the Terragnolo Valley, revealed a well-preserved moraine sequence at 700 m, composed of diamicton with a silty matrix, indicating significant local glacial activity following the retreat of the Atesino Glacier. A comparison with the Posina Valley provided key insights into the chronology of local glacial expansion. Here, a paleosol was identified at the base of the glacial deposits associated with the maximum advance of one of the Monte Pasubio glacier tongues. A wood fragment recovered from the paleosol serves as a valuable chronological marker for dating the local LGM. The interaction between the Atesino and Monte Pasubio glaciers appears to have been highly complex. The distribution of deposits suggests that the Monte Pasubio glacier had already reached significant elevations before the arrival of the Atesino Glacier. This interpretation is further supported by the higher orographic precipitation in this area compared to other Alpine regions, making it an interesting natural laboratory for studying the LGM in the Alps.